

HUMAN RIGHTS COALITION

TO: The Chairman and Members of the Parliamentary Select Committee on Constitutional, Legal and Parliamentary Affairs

From: The Human Rights Coalition

Honourable Chairman and members,

By notice dated September 15, 2021, the Parliamentary Service, on behalf of the Parliamentary Select Committee on Constitutional, Legal and Parliamentary Affairs, issued a request for written memoranda on the Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021 (“the Bill”). It is in response to this request that the Human Rights Coalition respectfully submits this Memorandum. We hope that our memo will assist the Committee in its deliberations.

MEMORANDUM TO PARLIAMENTARY SELECT COMMITTEE ON CONSTITUTIONAL, LEGAL AND PARLIAMENTARY AFFAIRS ON THE 'PROMOTION OF PROPER HUMAN SEXUAL RIGHTS AND GHANAIAN FAMILY VALUES BILL, 2021' BY THE HUMAN RIGHTS COALITION

September 30, 2021

Executive Summary

The Human Rights Coalition is a coalition of human rights advocacy groups and civil society organisations in Ghana led by the Ghana Center for Democratic Development (CDD-Ghana) that are united behind a common agenda of ensuring that the fundamental human rights guaranteed in Ghana's Constitution and other applicable legal instruments are enjoyed on equal terms by all the people of Ghana, including, especially by vulnerable and marginalised social minorities. The full list of the members of the Human Rights Coalition is provided at the end of the memo.

The purpose of this Memorandum is to assist the Committee in its review and consideration of the *Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021*. The Bill seeks, in a nutshell, to criminalise LGBTQ+ sexual relationships and associations. The Bill also criminalises directly or indirectly a wide range of other conduct. Some of the Bill's proscriptions also apply to non-LGBTQ+ persons.

1. Public Policy Justifications for the Bill

(i) The "no right is absolute" argument

Proponents of the Bill seek to justify the far-reaching and unprecedented restrictions the Bill imposes on LGBTTQQIAAP+ persons ('LGBTQ+' or 'LGBTQ+ persons') and persons who might wish to assist LGBTQ+ persons by stating that rights are not absolute and can lawfully be restricted. We acknowledge, of course, that the rights at issue here¹ are not absolute. But neither is the power of the State to restrict a right.

In order to ensure the maximum possible protection for those rights guaranteed under the 1992 Constitution ('Constitution'), the Constitution sets a high bar for any law that seeks or purports to restrict any such right. Not only must a law seeking to interfere with a right be specifically justified on certain legitimate public interest grounds, but the prohibition and other regulatory provisions of that law must be shown to be

¹ Right to privacy [Article 18(2) of the Constitution]; freedom of speech and expression [Article 21(1)(a) of the Constitution]; freedom of assembly [Article 21(1)(d) of the Constitution]; freedom of association [Article 21(1)(e) of the Constitution]; right to non-discrimination [Article 17(1) and (2) of the Constitution]

reasonably required or necessary for realising the legitimate public goals that provide the grounds for the bill. The rationale for this high standard of scrutiny is to prevent legislation from being deployed willy-nilly to destroy or claw back fundamental constitutional rights.

The far-reaching restrictions the Bill imposes on LGBTQ+ persons and persons who might wish to assist LGBTQ+ persons include: Clause 4 which prohibits a person from engaging in acts that undermine the proper human sexual rights and Ghanaian family values provided for in the Bill; Clause 6 which prohibits sexual relations between persons of the same sex and Clause 12 which prohibits advocacy, promotion and support for LGBTQ+ rights and related activities. Others are Clause 14 which prohibits funding or sponsorship for LGBTQ+ related activities; Clauses 15 and 16 which prohibit all forms of associations which offer support for LGBTQ+ persons and related activities.

Neither the grounds proffered by the Bill's sponsors as the policy justifications for the Bill nor these specific prohibitions and methods the Bill adopts can pass the high bar the Constitution sets for any law that seeks to interfere with a right guaranteed and deemed fundamental by the Constitution.

Proponents of the Bill are unable to establish or demonstrate by any concrete or provable facts, data, or science how or in what ways the hypothetical harms they conjecture up are attributable to LGBTQ+ persons or their everyday activities or how criminalising LGBTQ+ persons or their activities and associations would avert the "parable of horrors" or doomsday scenario they say would result from our continuing to co-exist peacefully with LGBTQ+ persons. The fact that LGBTQ+ persons are already part of our community, and have been from time immemorial, but have not caused us to experience any of the parade of horrors conjured up by the Bill's proponents shows that the untold social harms that are said to arise from toleration of LGBTQ+ persons or their activities are little more than a scare tactic.

The Bill's proponents make a feeble attempt to find a public health justification to the Bill by throwing up the statistic that about 18.1% of persons living with HIV/AIDS are men who sleep with men. What the Bill's proponents somehow fail to realise, however, is that, on its flip side, this very statistic means that roughly four-fifths of persons living with HIV/AIDS, the overwhelming majority of HIV/AIDS cases, bear no relationship to LGBTQ+ persons or activities.

Instead of focusing obsessively on LGBTQ+ persons, the Bill's sponsors, if they are sincerely concerned about the health consequences and costs of sexual activity, should concern themselves with all forms of irresponsible or risky sexual behaviour, whether between heterosexuals or LGBTQ+ persons, as that arguably is where the problem lies.

The appropriate public policy intervention then, is not a law that singles out LGBTQ+ persons or their activities for criminalisation; it is an intervention that ensures that all

potentially sexually active persons, whether LGBTQ+ or heterosexual, are provided adequate and appropriate education on responsible sex or sexual behaviour as well as access to medical advice and care.

(ii) State regulation of sexual behaviour

Generally, when it comes to sex, states have drawn the line at consent and capacity. Sex or sexual relations in which at least one of these two elements—consent and capacity—is missing on one side of the encounter is traditionally a prime candidate for criminalisation. This explains the universal criminalisation of rape, defilement, incest, and bestiality. Moreover, because sex is regarded as an intimately private affair, sex that is performed in reasonable view of the public also tends to be criminalised as indecent.

Beyond these categories (consent, capacity, privacy), criminalisation of sex is generally lacking in public interest justification. That, for example, explains why the criminal law typically does not concern itself with adultery or premarital sex not involving a minor. These areas of sex are typically left to personal morality and moral education. Where consent, capacity, and privacy are all present, criminalisation of same-sex sex but not heterosexual sex raises questions of gender discrimination. It also ignores the fact that the sexual acts prohibited among same-sex partners are also acts that heterosexual partners can—and some do—freely engage in, making the singling out of the same sexual activity between LGBTQ+ persons all the more unreasonable and harder to justify.

It is important in this context to distinguish regulation of same-sex sex from same-sex marriage. Marriage is a public institution; sex is not. Sex is a private affair. Accordingly, the state is generally within its right to prescribe reasonable conditions or qualifications beyond mutual consent and mutual capacity in order for one to be entitled to be issued a marriage license or certificate. Sex being natural in its origin, not an activity created or licensed by the state, regulation by the state beyond consent, capacity and privacy simply smacks of totalitarianism.

(iii) The Cultural values justification for the Bill

Proponents of the Bill also attempt to justify its sweeping and draconian provisions on the grounds that they promote Ghanaian cultural values. The Constitution of Ghana, not any aspect of Ghanaian culture, is the supreme law of the land and, therefore, the measuring rod or standard against which the validity of any Bill must first be evaluated. Cultural norms and practices, no matter how widely shared among Ghanaians, are themselves subject to the Constitution. Contrary to the Constitution's prescriptions, nearly all of the provisions of this Bill and the assumptions and prejudices driving them directly dehumanise LGBTQ+ persons, in some cases comparing them implicitly to animals and the mentally incompetent. And this, for no reason other than the mere fact of their sexual identity as LGBTQ+ persons. In fact,

the Bill does not accord any dignity whatsoever to LGBTQ+ persons. To the contrary, it treats them as so undeserving of equal consideration, respect, and dignity, that it is happy to condemn them to the status of social pariahs and second-class citizens.

It goes to the extent of criminalising those who would extend help, empathy, even shelter to LGBTQ+ persons. Nothing could be more psychologically and mentally injurious to the health of our LGBTQ+ compatriots. The Constitution does not permit this sort of indignity to be visited upon any group of persons in the name of culture or cultural values or, for that matter, of religion.

(iv) The marriage and family justification

Proponents of the Bill further defend it by making copious reference to the importance of family and marriage and proffer as support for this position international instruments like the International Covenant on Economic, Social, and Cultural Affairs, and the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights. However, what the Bill's proponents fail to do, yet again, is show or demonstrate how same-sex relations or any LGBTQ+ practices endanger family life or marriage. Beyond mere assertion, the proponents of the Bill do not demonstrate or establish in what ways LGBTQ+ persons represent a threat either to the family or to marriage. LGBTQ+ persons have made no affirmative demands of any kind on anybody, society, or the state. How asking to be let alone threatens family life or the institution of marriage is hard to fathom.

(v) Prohibiting advocacy for the rights of LGBTQ+ persons

The Memorandum also justifies the Bill's prohibition of advocacy for the rights of LGBTQ+ persons, by presenting advocates and other allies of LGBTQ+ persons as evil marauders seeking to proselytise younger, vulnerable persons, who are 'lured to assimilate the otherwise unacceptable forms of sexual expressions [sic] and who indulge in rapacious activities, and take advantage of destitute youth; 'easy prey'.

The Memorandum to the Bill further speaks of 'credible' reports from the Coalition for Proper Human Sexual Rights and Family Values, one of the primary movers behind the Bill, that indicate that some 'young persons are promised travel opportunities, allowances and other gifts...'. Others who play middlemen roles and connect young persons to LGBTQ+ persons are paid commissions, according to this report. As usual, these statements and allegations are not only unsubstantiated, they are calculated to stigmatise, degrade and induce fear and hatred of LGBTQ+ persons.

If the cited report is to be believed notwithstanding its source, what it describes bears close resemblance to sex trafficking and commercial sex, both of which are already prohibited under our laws.

There are also insinuations that LGBTQ+ persons are sexual predators and pedophiles. It is a notorious fact, however, that the cases of pedophilia, rape, defilement and other forms of child sexual abuse that are frequently reported in our media or handled by our criminal justice system, not to mention sexual harassment of

pupils by their teachers, almost always involve heterosexual men as the perpetrators. The proponents of this Bill, however, choose to be blind to this ugly fact and, instead, bear false witness by naming LGBTQ+ persons as the peculiar source of these criminal activities and social menace. Singling out LGBTQ+ persons for punitive discrimination, when, in fact, the overwhelming evidence points to non-LGBTQ+ persons as being more culpable in the commission of sex crimes, is just more of the same scare mongering, designed to besmear LGBTQ+ persons and thereby make them targets of social hatred and worse.

(vi) The 'support for victim' justification

The Memorandum also seeks to justify the Bill by claiming that some LGBTQ+ persons are simply vulnerable persons who, due to supposed financial hardship, have been forced into having these sexual relations. The Bill thus offers to provide 'support for victims'.

This rationale is, in fact, an essential part of the grand design of the proponents of the Bill to push and force acceptance of their ideological view that the LGBTQ+ identity is a false or artificial identity and that LGBTQ+ persons simply choose to be so and, therefore, can easily be helped to become "normal" if they are so inclined. If being LGBTQ+ is an optional choice, if it is an identity that LGBTQ+ persons can switch on and off, then, the argument goes, others can easily be induced, especially with financial inducements, to choose that "lifestyle". On this theory, economic vulnerability forces presumably heterosexual persons to choose to become LGBTQ+ persons. The other side of this argument is that, some persons are supposedly stuck in their LGBTQ+ identities because they do not have the resources to escape their condition. Again, the upshot of this argument is the unsubstantiated belief of the Bill's proponents that the LGBTQ+ identity is false or mutable.

(vii) The Bill and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

The Bill's sponsors go the extent of suggesting that the Bill's purposes and methods are in alignment with the SDGs. They begin with Goal 3 of the SDGs, which commits the State to ensure healthy lives and wellbeing for all. This health rationale for the Bill, like the others, is spurious. Criminalising LGBTQ+ persons and related activities, including assistance for LGBTQ+ persons, means that LGBTQ+ persons would shy away from accessing health care. This includes those LGBTQ+ persons who might have STIs or HIV/AIDS or who might need mental health assistance. Rather than promote realisation of SDG Goal 3, this Bill will do exactly the opposite: It will subvert the SDG Goals by leaving LGBTQ+ persons behind.

(viii) The Bill as a preventer of “mob violence”

The Memorandum claims that the Bill seeks to prevent instant or mob [in] justice by persons opposed to LGBTQ+. This is a case of the disease professing to be the cure. The truth of the matter is that, but for the stigmatisation and hate that bills and crusades of this kind mobilise and direct against LGBTQ+ persons, there would be little social “tension” or mob violence to worry about. The mischief here is the Bill itself.

2. The Bill is incompatible with Ghana’s international obligations

Ghana has obligations under international and regional human rights law to respect, protect, and fulfill human rights to all persons in its jurisdiction. Ghana is, therefore, obligated to ensure that the provisions of any measure which may become law is in consonance with Ghana’s binding obligations under international law, including regional human rights treaties.

The Bill is incompatible with the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, United Nations Charter, International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR), International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR), Convention on the Rights of the Child, International Convention on the Protection of the Rights of All Migrant Workers and Members of Their Families, African Charter on Human and People’s Rights and general principles of International Law.

3. Socio-economic and health implications for minority groups

Though data produced in consort with Ghanaian state institutions are scarce, the available evidence from non-state sources indicate that LGBTQ+ persons are likely subjected to higher forms of discrimination in the workplace and education. The passage of this Bill will doubtlessly exacerbate this trend ushering in discrimination in the domain of education, employment, health, and housing, compromising the rights of the groups targeted, which are guaranteed by the International Covenant on Economic Social and Cultural Rights, the Convention on the Rights of the Child and Chapter 5 of Ghana’s Constitution. Furthermore, the bill could also facilitate blackmail due to Clause 5, which imposes the duty to report persons suspected of having banned identities or engaging in banned activities.

4. Conclusion

It is the considered position of the Human Rights Coalition that the Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021 is irredeemably flawed, unconstitutional and needless. It does not address any pertinent cultural, socio-economic or political challenge the country faces. We respectfully ask the Committee to not recommend its passage.

MEMORANDUM

TO: The Honourable Chairman and Members
Committee on Constitutional, Legal and Parliamentary Affairs

FROM: THE HUMAN RIGHTS COALITION

SUBJECT: Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values
Bill, 2021

DATE: September 30, 2021

CC: Office of the Attorney-General

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1. Introduction

The Human Rights Coalition is grateful to your Committee for the opportunity to submit this memorandum. The purpose of this Memorandum is to assist the Committee in its review and consideration of the *Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021*.

The Human Rights Coalition is coalition of human rights advocacy groups and civil society organisations in Ghana that are united behind a common agenda of ensuring that the fundamental human rights guaranteed in Ghana’s Constitution and other applicable legal instruments are enjoyed on equal terms by all the people of Ghana, including, especially by vulnerable and marginalised social minorities. The members of the Coalition include Amnesty International, Ghana; [REDACTED] [REDACTED] [REDACTED] [REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]. The full list of the members of the Human Rights Coalition is provided at the end of the memo.

By notice dated September 15, 2021, the Parliamentary Service, on behalf of the Parliamentary Select Committee on Constitutional, Legal and Parliamentary Affairs, issued a request for written memoranda on the *Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021* (“the Bill”). It is in response to this request that we respectfully submit this Memorandum.

The current version of the Bill is 19 pages, has 25 clauses and a Memorandum which is 17 pages in length. It was presented to the Speaker of Parliament on June 29, 2021, by a group of eight (8) Parliamentarians led by Mr. Sam Nartey George, MP for Ningo-Prampram. It is our understanding that the Bill was formally introduced in the House on August 2, 2021.

The Bill seeks, in a nutshell, to criminalise LGBTQ+ sexual relationships and associations. The Bill also criminalises directly or indirectly a wide range of other conduct. Some of the Bill's proscriptions also apply to non-LGBTQ+ persons.

2. Public Policy Justifications for the Bill

(i) The “no right is absolute” argument

The Memorandum to this Bill seeks to justify why the right to advocate for the rights of LGBTTQQIAAP+ persons (‘LGBTQ+’ or ‘LGBTQ+ persons’) should be criminalised, by referring to the fact that rights are not absolute and are subject to certain restrictions. We, of course, acknowledge that the rights at issue here are not absolute. But neither is any law that purports to restrict or limit such a right. Rights would be meaningless if all it took to eliminate them was to pass or implement a law expressly designed to undo or destroy the right in question. In order to ensure the maximum possible protection for a right guaranteed under the 1992 Constitution (‘Constitution’), the Constitution sets a high bar for any law that seeks or purports to restrict such a right. Not only must a law seeking to interfere with a right be specifically justified on certain legitimate public interest grounds, but the prohibition and other regulatory provisions of the law must be shown to be reasonably required or necessary for realising the legitimate public goals that provide the grounds for the bill. In other words, there must be a demonstrable nexus between the means or methods adopted by the legislation in question and the ultimate public interest it purports or seeks to vindicate, which interest must itself be one that the Constitution considers legitimate. The rationale for this high standard of scrutiny is to prevent legislation from being deployed pretextually or willy-nilly to destroy or claw back fundamental constitutional rights.

Neither the grounds proffered by the Bill’s sponsors as the policy justifications for the Bill nor the prohibitions and other methods the Bill adopts pass the high bar the Constitution sets for any law that seeks to interfere with a right guaranteed and deemed fundamental by the Constitution. The Bill’s proponents cite the Vigilantism and Related Offences Act, 2019 (Act 999) and the Cybersecurity Act 2020, (Act 1038) to substantiate the fact that rights, in this case the rights to freedom of assembly, speech, association and privacy, may be restricted. But what the sponsors of the Bill must show by way of constitutional

justification is not mere reference to examples of laws that arguably meet or pass the constitutional test. Every Bill must stand or fall on its own weight, not lean on others for support. Moreover, the two statutes cited in support of this Bill's naked attack on fundamental constitutional rights fail to provide the Bill's sponsors with the analogy they seek to rely upon. Unlike this Bill, both statutes lie properly in the domain of national security. Not only is the State's interest in that area an objectively legitimate one, there is also a demonstrable, empirically provable nexus or connection between the activity the State prohibits or regulates in those two statutes and the policy justifications or grounds for each of the laws. For instance, our experience as a country has shown that left unchecked, "vigilantism" of the kind prohibited under the Vigilantism and Related Offences Act has the propensity to create far-reaching social chaos and disruption of public law and order. The carefully-tailored restrictions imposed on the rights to freedom of assembly and association under that law are thus justified on those grounds. It is similarly easy to see why certain limited restrictions are imposed on the right to privacy under the Cybersecurity Act 2020, (Act 1038). This Bill is woefully wanting in similar provable justification. The Memorandum to the Bill is unable to establish or demonstrate by any concrete or provable facts, data, or science on how or in what ways the hypothetical harms the Bill's proponents conjecture up are attributable to LGBTQ+ persons or their everyday activities or how criminalising LGBTQ+ persons or their activities and associations would avert the "parable of horrors" or doomsday scenario that the Bill's proponents say would result from the existence of LGBTQ+ persons or their activities and associations. They do not show us any instance, here or elsewhere, where that doomsday scenario has materialised. The fact that LGBTQ+ persons are already part of our community, and have been from time immemorial, yet we have experienced none of the parade of horrors conjured up by the Bill's proponents shows that these social harms that are said to arise from LGBTQ+ persons or their activities are little more than a scare tactic.

The Memorandum to the Bill neither demonstrates how LGBTQ+ infringes on the rights and freedoms of others nor how the private sexual or affective relations of mutually consenting adults of sound mind, whether heterosexual or same-sex, is contrary to any of the public interest grounds admissible as legitimate grounds for restricting the fundamental rights of LGBTQ+ persons. In an attempt to find a public health justification to the Bill, the Memorandum to the Bill throws up some statistics alleging that about 18.1% of persons living with HIV/AIDS are men who sleep with men. What the Bill's proponents somehow fail to realise is that this statistic, assuming it is correct, also suggests that roughly four-fifths of persons living with HIV/AIDS, the overwhelming majority of HIV/AIDS cases, bear no relationship to LGBTQ+ persons or activities. In effect, the Bill's singular focus on and obsession with LGBTQ+ persons is misplaced and, indeed, irresponsible from a public health perspective, as it glosses over the bulk of HIV/AIDS cases that evidently have nothing to do with LGBTQ+ persons. The problem then is not the mere fact of same sex relations, but all forms of risky sexual behaviour, whether between heterosexual or sex-same persons.

Given this reality, the appropriate public policy intervention is not a law that singles out LGBTQ+ persons or their activities for criminalisation; the appropriate intervention is to ensure that all potentially sexually active persons, whether LGBTQ+ or heterosexual, are provided adequate and appropriate education on responsible sex or sexual behaviour as well as access to medical advice and care. Criminalisation has been shown to be an ineffective tool in efforts to reduce transmission of sexually transmitted infections and HIV/AIDS. More than ineffective, criminalisation is decidedly counterproductive. According to the United Nations Programme on HIV/AIDS (UNAIDS), countries with progressive laws and policies and inclusive health systems have had the best outcomes against HIV. Being inclusive reduces stigma and discrimination against the LGBTQ+ community, allowing its members to access appropriate medical care, education and support that will, in turn, promote the health and wellbeing of the wider population.

(ii) State regulation of sexual behaviour

State regulation of sexual relations is not new. Because sex or sexual relations might involve abuse, exploitation, the use of force, or persons who are not legally competent or capable of participating consensually in sex, state regulation of sexual relations is easily justifiable to protect against these harms. In general, when it comes to sex, states have drawn the line at consent and capacity. Therefore, sex or sexual relations in which at least one of these two elements is missing on one side of the affair or encounter is traditionally a prime candidate for criminalisation. This explains the universal criminalisation of rape, defilement, incest, and bestiality. In each of these instances, the consent or capacity (or both consent and capacity) on the part of one of the parties is determined, either subjectively or objectively, to be lacking. In addition, because sex is regarded as an intimately private affair, sex in public also tends to be criminalised as indecent.

Beyond these categories (consent, capacity, privacy), criminalisation of sex is generally lacking in public interest justification. That, for example, explains why the criminal law typically does not concern itself with adultery or premarital sex not involving a minor. These areas of sex are typically left to personal morality and moral education. It also explains why state regulation or criminalisation of private consensual sex among same-sex adults is highly contested as lacking in public interest justification. This accounts for the increasing decriminalisation of such sex in jurisdictions across the world, including in Africa. Where they remain criminalised, the grounds have remained largely puritanical, as was the case when laws criminalising same-sex sex were first introduced in Africa and elsewhere. Such puritanical grounds, rooted in religion, are, however, not considered sufficient to warrant or justify interference by a secular state.

Where consent, capacity, and privacy are all present, criminalization of same-sex sex but not heterosexual sex raises questions of sex and gender discrimination. It also ignores the fact that the sexual acts prohibited among same-sex partners are also acts that heterosexual partners can—and some do—freely engage in, making the singling out of the same sexual activity between LGBTQ+ persons all the more unreasonable and harder to justify except on puritanical grounds. We have already shown that the public health justification often given for the distinction or discrimination is simply spurious, as risky or harmful sex, leading to all manner of STIs and other social consequences such as teenage pregnancy, is generally more prevalent among heterosexuals than same-sex partners. Moreover, criminalisation of any particular form of sex on public health grounds has been shown to be counter-productive, as it merely drives the affected population underground and cuts them off from access to health-related education and treatment.

It is important in this context to distinguish same-sex from same-sex marriage. Marriage is a public institution; sex is not. Sex is a private affair. Accordingly, the state is generally within its right to prescribe reasonable conditions or qualifications beyond mutual consent and mutual capacity for one to be entitled to be issued a marriage license or certificate. Sex being natural in its origin, not an activity created or licensed by the state, regulation by the same beyond consent, capacity and privacy simply smacks of totalitarianism.

Another way of putting this is that, the right to express oneself sexually or engage in sexual relations falls within the category of “negative rights”. It is an intimately private right, the exercise and expression of which, by and between mutually consenting adults, is fundamental to one’s personhood and dignity as a human being. It is not a “positive right,” meaning that, it is not a right that emanates from or is created by the State, and, as long as it is enjoyed privately by and among mutually consenting adults and is free of commercial or other forms of exploitation or abuse, the State, in a free and democratic society, overreaches in trying to restrict or interfere in such relations. By seeking to

criminalise a whole range of sex-related activities of LGBTQ+ persons, as well as activities involving no sex whatsoever, the Bill would confer on the Government of Ghana unprecedented and wide-ranging powers of a tyrannical kind--powers that, instructively, the Government itself has not sought or found necessary to seek.

(iii) The Cultural values justification for the Bill

Proponents of the Bill also attempt to justify its sweeping and draconian provisions on the grounds that they promote Ghanaian cultural values. This has become a common tactic of proponents of these types of bills that have been making the rounds in various authoritarian states across the world. To mask their origins in an international right-wing crusade, backed by religious interests, the strategy of the crusaders has been to try to “indigenise” or localise the campaign in each target country by invoking the “cultural values” of each target society as justification for the bill. In Ghana’s case, this attempt cannot pass constitutional muster.

First of all, the Constitution, not any aspect of Ghanaian culture, is the supreme law of the land and the measuring rod or standard against which any Bill must first be evaluated. Importantly, Ghanaian cultural norms and practices, no matter how widely shared, are themselves subject to the Constitution. Notably, Article 26 of the Constitution outlaws “All cultural practices which dehumanise or are injurious to the physical and mental wellbeing of a person.” This statement is emphasised yet again in the Directive Principles of State Policy where the State is commanded, in Article 39(3), to “ensure . . . that traditional practices which are injurious to the health and well-being of THE PERSON are abolished.” In short, unlike the Bill, it is the dignity and the physical and mental wellbeing of the individual person that is of paramount concern to the Constitution.

Nearly all of the provisions of this Bill and the assumptions and prejudices driving them directly dehumanise LGBTQ+ persons, in some cases comparing them implicitly to animals and the mentally incompetent. And this, for no reason other than the mere fact of their sexual identity as LGBTQ+ persons. In fact, the Bill does not accord any dignity whatsoever to LGBTQ+ persons. To the contrary, it treats them as so undeserving of equal consideration, respect, and dignity, that it is happy to condemn them to the status of social pariahs and second-class citizens. It goes to the extent of criminalising those who would extend help, empathy, even shelter to LGBTQ+ persons. Nothing could be more psychologically and mentally injurious to the health of our LGBTQ+ compatriots. The Constitution does not permit this sort of indignity to be visited upon any group of persons in the name of culture or cultural values or, for that matter, of religion. Instead, what the Constitution rightfully affirms, in Article 15(1), is that “The dignity of ALL persons shall be inviolable.” The Bill very explicitly and unashamedly offends this most basic and unequivocal of commands, among others.

All persons are, of course, free to practice and participate in the enjoyment and expression of their respective cultures, just as they are their religion. Article 26(1) is clear about that. Beyond that, the Constitution does not subscribe to any monolithic Ghanaian culture or religion, and most definitely does not prescribe the imposition on any individual or group or community, on penalty of imprisonment or a fine, of any religious dogma or belief or, for that matter, any Ghanaian cultural value, norm, or practice. Rather, the State is commanded to “take steps to ENCOURAGE the integration of appropriate customary values into the fabric of the nation THROUGH FORMAL AND INFORMAL EDUCATION . . .”.

(iv) The marriage and family justification

The Memorandum to the Bill justifies the need for such a law with detailed reference to the importance of family and marriage and provides international instruments like the International Covenant on Economic, Social, and Cultural Affairs, and the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights. However, it does not directly explain how same-sex relations or any LGBTQ+ practices endanger family life. It sounds rather odd that, LGBTQ+ persons who, under our laws, cannot marry are deemed by this Bill to be a threat to family life. Again, beyond mere assertion, the proponents of the Bill do not demonstrate or establish in what ways LGBTQ+ persons, in Ghana or anywhere else, are a threat to family life. If anything, it is this Bill that seeks to break family and social cohesion by inciting and legitimising hatred toward LGBTQ+ persons and encouraging families and society to disown or withdraw empathy and support for LGBTQ+ persons.

Instructively, the societies in which LGBTQ+ persons or activities are tolerated have not suffered social disintegration or a destruction of family life on account of that fact. To the contrary, some of these same societies have some of the most generous and most humane pro-family social policies, including government-funded assistance to vulnerable families. What we should be learning and borrowing from these societies, if anything, are their pro-family social policies and benefits, not their ideological and religious dogma-inspired culture wars.

(v) Prohibiting advocacy for the rights of LGBTQ+ persons

The Memorandum also addresses the issue of prohibiting advocacy for rights of the LGBTQ+ community, by presenting advocates for the rights and sexual freedoms of the LGBTQ+ as evil marauders seeking to proselytise younger, vulnerable persons, who are *'lured to assimilate the otherwise unacceptable forms of sexual expressions [sic] and who indulge in rapacious activities, and take advantage of destitute youth; 'easy prey'*. These and similar statements are not only unsubstantiated, they are stigmatising, isolating, degrading, and calculated to induce fear and hatred of the LGBTQ+ community and its allies by painting LGBTQ+ persons as pedophiles. This language is inconsistent with Ghana's obligations under international human rights law, being in violation of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, particularly Articles 1 and 2, which are founded on the principles of equality and non-discrimination.

The Memorandum to the Bill further speaks of *'credible'* reports from the Coalition for Proper Human Sexual Rights and Family Values, one of the primary movers behind the Bill, that indicate that some *'young persons are promised travel opportunities, allowances and other gifts...'*. Others who play middlemen roles and connect young persons to LGBTQ+ persons are paid commissions, according to this report.

If this report is to be believed notwithstanding its source, what it describes bears close resemblance to sex trafficking and commercial sex, both of which are already prohibited under our laws. Importantly, the cases of pedophilia, defilement and other forms of child sexual abuse that are frequently reported in our media or handled by our criminal justice system, including sexual harassment of pupils by their teachers, involve heterosexual men. Yet the proponents of this Bill, ignoring these notorious facts and the overwhelming body of evidence pointing in a different direction, would rather have us believe that LGBTQ+ persons are a peculiar source of this social menace. This is more of the same

scare mongering, designed to besmear LGBTQ+ persons and make them targets of social hatred and worse.

(vi) The 'support for victim' justification

The Memorandum also seeks to justify the Bill by presenting some members of the LGBTQ+ community as vulnerable persons who, due to supposed financial constraints, have been forced into having these sexual relations. It thus claims to provide '*support for victims*'. This rationale is essential to the grand design of the proponents of the Bill to push and force acceptance of their view that the LGBTQ+ identity is a false or artificial identity and that LGBTQ+ persons simply choose to be so and, therefore, can easily be helped to become "normal" if they are so inclined. If being LGBTQ+ is an optional choice, if it is an identity that LGBTQ+ persons can switch on and off, then, the argument goes, others can easily be induced, especially with financial inducements, to choose that "lifestyle". On this theory, economic vulnerability forces presumably heterosexual persons to choose to become LGBTQ+ persons, just like similar vulnerability presumably drives some women to become "side chicks" or "slay queens". The other side of the argument is that, some persons are supposedly stuck in their LGBTQ+ identities because they do not have the resources to escape those identities. Again, the upshot of this argument is the belief of the Bill's proponents that the LGBTQ+ identity is mutable.

Unfortunately, the proponents of this Bill claim omniscience in a matter about which knowledge and understanding continues to evolve. Disregarding the experience of LGBTQ+ persons themselves, the Bill's sponsors and supporters, presumably not LGBTQ+ themselves, somehow claim to know full and final knowledge, the one and only eternal truth, about the LGBTQ+ identity. And standing on that presumably unassailable knowledge, they proffer so-called "conversion therapy" or else criminalisation and social death as the remedy. In the absolutism of their certainty as to the rightness of their belief and knowledge on this matter, the proponents of the Bill, unfortunately, follow in the tradition of those who, standing on the religious dogma of the day, once believed the

Earth to be flat and any contrary belief to be heretical. Just as the astronomer Galileo was forced by the Papacy and the Catholic hierarchy of his times to “recant” his hypothesis and finding that the Earth rotated daily and revolved around the sun and spent the rest of his life under house arrest, the proponents of this Bill believing themselves to already know it all when it came to matters of LGBTQ+ and to have found the one “proper human sexuality” for all times, insist that LGBTQ+ persons “recant” and be “helped” through “conversion therapy” treatment or else risk imprisonment. What this Bill seeks to do, essentially, is to freeze scientific inquiry and close debate on a matter about which our state of knowledge is necessarily incomplete and evolving.

What the proponents of the Bill do not tell us is why wealthy LGBTQ+ persons, whether here or elsewhere, who do not have to worry about the constraint of money, have not all rushed to put themselves and their loved ones through this supposedly liberating “conversion therapy”. Given the hostility, discrimination and marginalisation that most LGBTQ+ persons face, the proponents of the Bill again fail to explain why any person, who could otherwise easily be heterosexual and thereby enjoy social acceptance and all the privileges that come with it, would choose rationally to be LGBTQ+. The ultimate suggestion implicit in the argument of the Bill’s proponents has to be that, LGBTQ+ identity is “abnormal” and LGBTQ+ persons mentally or psychologically troubled and irrational. It is this line of thinking, not any credible science or empirical data, that leads the sponsors of the Bill to the discredited idea of conversion therapy. It is a line of thinking that further degrades and stigmatises LGBTQ+ persons in order to justify their treatment as less than human, which is precisely what the Bill seeks to do.

(vii) The Bill and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

It is curious that the Memorandum to the Bill seeks to justify the need for the Bill by resorting to claims that it aligns with the SDGs. Goal 3, which requires the State to ensure healthy lives and wellbeing for all. As we have already demonstrated, this other rationale for the Bill, like the others, is simply without basis. Criminalising LGBTQ+ persons and related activities, including assistance for LGBTQ+ persons, means that LGBTQ+ persons would shy away from accessing health care. This includes those LGBTQ+ persons who might have STIs or HIV/AIDS or who might need mental health assistance. Rather than promote realisation of SDG Goal 3, this Bill will do exactly the opposite: It will subvert the SDG Goals by leaving LGBTQ+ persons behind.

Take for example, SDG 5, which requires states to achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls. The Bill purports to align with this goal, yet the very basis of the Bill is to draw unreasonable distinctions among persons based on sex and gender and disempower certain groups on the basis of their gender identity. Thus, for example lesbian, bisexual, and transsexual women will be subject to criminal penalties, and others who support them, or advocate for their inclusion in national policies will also face criminal sanctions. The Bill is violently opposed to Goal 5 and seeks to not only deepen inequalities between men and women, but also between heterosexual and non-heterosexual women. This is also inconsistent with Ghana's obligations under other international instruments like the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women.

Again, the Memorandum and the Bill are internally inconsistent, as the purpose of the Bill is directly at odds with Goal 10. The Memorandum claims that the Bill seeks to do away with harassment and discrimination of "a proportion of the population reporting to having personally felt discriminated against or harassed in the previous twelve months on the basis of a ground of discrimination prohibited under international human rights."

This contradicts the basis, language and spirit of the Bill, which not only seeks to criminalise LGBTQ+ practices, which in itself is discrimination, it criminalises even those who provide support, or advocate for their rights, or who seek to empower persons within the LGBTQ+ community. In short, The Bill makes claims of inclusion and non-discrimination, while advocating social isolation and exclusion as well as discrimination against LGBTQ+. It preaches virtue, yet practises vice, so to speak.

(viii) The Bill as mediator

Finally, the Bill purports to mediate the social tensions between members of the LGBTQ+ community and others in opposition. The Memorandum claims that it is to avoid instant or mob [in] justice by persons opposed to LGBTQ+. The irony of the matter is that, but for the stigmatisation and incitement of hatred that bills and crusades of the kind that animate this Bill purposefully direct against LGBTQ+ persons, there would be no social “tension” to worry about. In that regard, to say that this Bill is needed to protect LGBTQ+ persons from their haters, is equivalent to the disease professing to be the cure.

As it is not the LGBTQ+ community that the Memorandum claims would cause the disorder and violence, it is strange that it is that community that should be the target of punitive sanctions, rather than those who resort to violence to express their preferences. If the Bill seeks to protect the LGBTQ community from violence, then it should rather champion their rights, and use the criminal law against persons who target members of the LGBTQ+ community, resorting to violence as a means of enforcing compulsory heterosexuality. The Bill cannot, in one breath purport to protect a community, while at the same time attacking the very identity, and lived realities of that community.

3. Criminalisation of LGBTQ+ and related activities

(i) The 'traditional Ghanaian customs, beliefs and values' argument

Proponents of this private member's Bill argue that the proposed restrictions on the rights of LGBTQ+ persons are justified because LGBTQ+ persons and their activities do not conform to 'traditional Ghanaian customs, beliefs and values'. Clause 4 of the Bill provides that,

'a person shall not (a) undermine the proper human sexual rights and Ghanaian family values specified in Section 2 of this Act; or (b) directly or indirectly, instigate, command, counsel, procure, solicit, or in any other manner purposely aid, facilitate, encourage or promote, whether by a personal act of presence or otherwise, an act that undermines the proper human sexual rights and Ghanaian family values.'

A person who contravenes this provision is liable to a fine of between 1,000 penalty units (GHC 12,000) and 2,000 penalty units (GHC 24,000). Such a person may also be sentenced to a prison term of between 2 to 4 months.

We acknowledge that no right is absolute. But neither is a law that purports to restrict or limit a right. Rights would be meaningless if all it took to destroy them was the passage or implementation of any law aimed at destroying them. In order to ensure the maximum possible protection for a right guaranteed under the Constitution, the Constitution sets a high bar for any law that seeks or purports to restrict a guaranteed right. Among other things, the policy grounds for restricting the personal liberties of persons irrespective of their gender, ethnicity, faith or sexual orientation must align with grounds provided by and permissible under the *1992 Constitution* ('*Constitution*'). Chapter 5 of the Constitution sets forth grounds and the circumstances under which personal liberties may be restricted. The circumstances include where a person's liberties are restricted (i) in execution of a sentence or order of a court in respect of a criminal offence of which a person has been convicted [Article 14(1) (a)]; (ii) in execution of an order of a court

punishing a person for contempt of court [Article 14(1)(b)]; (iii) for the purpose of bringing a person before a court in execution of an order of a court [Article 14(1)(c)]; (iv) in the case of a person suffering from an infectious or contagious disease, a person of unsound mind, a person addicted to drugs or alcohol or a vagrant, for the purpose of his care or treatment or the protection of the community [Article 14(1)(d)]; and (v) for the purpose of the education or welfare of a person who has not attained the age of eighteen years [Article 14(1) (e)]. In addition, a person's right may be restricted 'for the purpose of preventing the unlawful entry of that person into Ghana, or of effecting the expulsion, extradition or other lawful removal of that person from Ghana or for the purpose of restricting that person while he is being lawfully conveyed through Ghana in the course of his extradition or removal from one country to another [Article 14(1)(h)]; or upon reasonable suspicion of his having committed or being about to commit a criminal offence under the laws of Ghana' [Article 14(1)(g)]. Evidently, Chapter 5 of the Constitution makes no provision for the restriction of personal liberties on the ground of 'traditional Ghanaian customs, beliefs and values.' "Culture" – as important as it is in other realms – cannot be invoked or used to override constitutional rights.

(ii) The State cannot micromanage sexual relations between consenting adults without justification

Clause 6 of the Bill provides, among others, that, '*a person commits an offence if the person (a) engages in (i) sexual intercourse between or among persons of the same sex; (ii) sexual intercourse between a man and an animal or a woman and an animal; or (iii) pansexual activity...*'

Proponents of this provision justify it on the premise that, '*LGBTQQIAAP+ activities threaten the concept of family and the associated value systems that are central to the social structure of all ethnic groups in Ghana*'. In addition, they appear to suggest that the social costs of sexual relations between LGBTQQIAAP+ persons are so egregious as to justify the evisceration of the rights of LGBTQQIAAP+ persons. This suggestion is based on

nothing but conjecture and subjective opinion. Proponents of this Bill no empirically supportable or scientifically incontestable evidence of the alleged social costs or the threat to 'the concept of family and the associated value systems' peculiarly associated with LGBTQ+ persons or their everyday activities.

First, it is important to recognise that any social cost presumably associated with sexual relations between LGBTTQQIAAP+ persons, if any, are not exceptional or peculiar. All sexual relations have their attendant social costs including the spread of Sexually Transmitted Diseases (STDs), adolescent pregnancies, etc. A government concerned about public health threats occasioned by risky sexual behavior, whether heterosexual or same-sex, has a slew of effective, non-intrusive options and instruments at its disposal, including, for example, policies and measures such as educating the public on safe sex (e.g. the use of contraceptives) or limiting the publication of sexual content in the media to certain times. Such restrictions on the right to engage in sexual relations or the right to access sexual content should be limited, proportional or narrowly tailored to the goal sought to be accomplished, and must not directly or indirectly eviscerate the affected rights, especially of mutually consenting adults.

Second, it is not the government's role to micromanage sexual relations between two consenting adults. Proponents of the Bill fail to understand the importance of the distinction between "positive rights," which demand active provisioning by the State, and "negative rights," which merely asks the State to leave individuals alone to enjoy the right as long as the rights and interests of others are not interfered with in the process.

The right to express oneself sexually or engage in sexual relations falls within the category of "negative rights". It is an intimately private right, the exercise and expression of which, by and between mutually consenting adults, is fundamental to one's personhood and dignity as a human being. It is not a right that emanates from or is created by the State, and, as long as it is enjoyed privately by and among mutually consenting adults and is free of commercial or other forms of exploitation or abuse, the State, in a free and

democratic society, overreaches in trying to restrict or interfere in such relations. By seeking to criminalise a whole range of sex-related activities of LGBTQ+ persons, as well as activities involving no sex whatsoever, the Bill would confer on the Government of Ghana unprecedented and wide-ranging powers of a tyrannical kind – powers that, instructively, the Government itself has not sought or found necessary to seek.

(iii) Criminalising advocacy for the rights of others

Clauses 12-16 of the Bill generally criminalise any form of association with, or advocacy for the rights of, LGBTTTQQIAAP+ persons, including funding for such activities. The Constitution guarantees the rights of all persons to assemble freely, to speak freely and band together to promote a cause (Article 21). The Ghanaian courts have given a number of decisions enforcing these rights, including the decision of the Supreme Court in the case of *New Patriotic Party v Inspector General of Police* [1993-94] 2 GLR 459 – 509. In resolving the key issues in that case, Amua-Sekyi JSC observed that,

'[e]xcept in time of war, or when a state of emergency has been declared, it cannot be right for any agency of the executive to suppress the free expression of any opinion, however unpopular that opinion may be. The believer in absolutism and the anarchist, those who support and those who are opposed to abortion, those who favour and those who oppose equal rights of women – yes, lesbians and homosexuals too – are all entitled to the free expression of their views, and the right to assemble and demonstrate in support of those views and to propagate those views.' [Emphasis added]

Given the relevant provisions of the Constitution guaranteeing these rights and the decisions of the courts enforcing same, Clauses 12-16 of the Bill which seeks to criminalise any form of association or advocacy for the rights of LGBTTTQQIAAP+ people is a direct infringement of the Constitution.

In a democratic dispensation where the rights of all persons, including social minorities, are guaranteed under the Constitution, any legislation that targets and singles out LGBT+ persons and denies them, by virtue of their status or identity as sexual minorities, rights otherwise available to all other persons, including, notably, the right to associate with each other and to assemble and advocate peacefully causes they consider to in their mutual or collective interest, subjects LGBTQ+ persons to grossly unequal and unfair treatment of the kind that clearly affronts the Constitution. Moreover, such a law would only serve to further oppress, marginalize and victimize the already socially marginalized LGBTQ+ persons. The Bill further overreaches by seeking to criminalization even allies of LGBTQ+ persons. The clear agenda here is to turn LGBTQ+ persons into social outcasts and untouchables, persons with whom others associate and try to assist or express solidarity with at their own peril. What the Bill seeks to accomplish through these bizarrely totalitarian provisions is to condemn LGBTQ+ persons to nothing short of social death.

4. Potential violations of Constitutional protections of fundamental human rights

(i) Clauses 12-14- Propaganda and advocacy

Clauses 12-14 of the Bill seek to criminalise various social, economic and community building activities which provide an avenue to express support or engage in discussion around the existence or expression of LGBTQ+ persons in Ghana. These clauses impose arbitrary limits on the fundamental human rights to education, association, personal liberty, free speech, use of personal property and provide license for more or less arbitrary censorship of traditional and social media.

As we have already noted, laws that seek to interfere with constitutionally guaranteed rights, including the rights to freedom of speech, expression, assembly and association, must, under the Constitution, pass a test of strict scrutiny. Such rights, being rights fundamental to one's dignity as a person as well as one's ability to participate on equal terms with others in a democratic society, cannot be simply wished away or displayed by mere passage of a law or recitation of a grounds that are constitutionally impermissible or unsupported by credible data or science.

The failure of the Bill to show or demonstrate unambiguously how or in what ways the infringements on the rights of LGBTQ+ persons are reasonably justifiable and necessary to realize a legitimate public interest is a fatal defect of the Bill.

(ii) Clause 12: Prohibition of propaganda of, promotion of and advocacy for activities prohibited under the Bill

Clause 12 (1) creates a second-degree felony out of the actions of a person, who by technological means, expresses or facilitates the expression of sentiments that can be interpreted as supportive of LGBTQ+. Clause 12 (3) further creates a second-degree felony out of the provision of any form of assistance, including the use of movable and

immovable property in furtherance of the promotion of a prohibited activity. The implications of such sweeping provisions is to make criminal various economic and advocacy activities that are a routine part of the democratic process. In criminalising advocacy in support of LGBTQ+ persons or causes, the Bill essentially outlaws open democratic debate and dialogue about an issue and presumes that one side of the issue, the side taken by the sponsors of the Bill, is the only repository of truth and knowledge, with all the answers, now and for all time, on the matter in controversy. Nothing in the Constitution remotely supports this kind or degree of intolerance or closed-mindedness. To the contrary, our Constitution, built, as it is, upon the foundations of pluralism, requires that the democratic process and public square be open to a multitude of opinions and expressions, reflecting the diversity of identities, interests, and opinion in our national community.

It is interesting to note that the scope of “prohibited activity” under this Bill is not exhaustive. So far as an activity exists outside of what the prosecuting authority deems to fall into a male or female binary, it suffices. Such vague catch-all provisions, aside from being chillingly reminiscent of authoritarian enactments like the Preventive Detention Act of 1958, are an open invitation for would-be enforcers of this Bill to abuse their enforcement powers. Indeed, taken at its word, the Bill would make criminal the work of many civil society organizations, and even some state agencies like the Commission on Human Rights and Administrative Justice (CHRAJ) and the Ghana AIDS Commission, whose mandates commit them to work with all persons on equal terms. Even Parliament would, under this Bill, have difficulty opening its doors and Committee processes to advocacy in support of LGBTQ+ persons.

(iii) Clause 13: Prohibition of propaganda, promotion, and advocacy for prohibited activities directed at children

This clause creates a second-degree felony on the part of persons who through traditional media (TV or radio) or social media directly or indirectly engage in activity which intends to evoke the interest of a child in an activity prohibited under the Bill, or intends to teach a child to explore sex or gender outside the binary category of male and female. Clause 13(2) further imputes liability to owners and principal officers of media or technology platforms on which such material is circulated. The vagueness of language in this clause raises particular concern as no definition of what “evoking the interest of a child directly or indirectly” means. The notion that the only way to protect minors from influences considered or deemed harmful to persons without the capacity of adults is to ban adults from engaging in that supposed activity is rather bizarre. If protection of minors were the principal motivation, the Bill could simply limit its reach to minors, as is commonly done with lawful products like alcohol and cigarettes, which adults are free to consume (as long as they do not endanger the public) but which by law are not permitted to be sold to or used by minor. When it comes to matter of sex, whether heterosexual or otherwise, what minors need from the State is age-appropriate sex and reproductive health education. The absence of that education is seen in the growing cases of child sexual abuse and teenage pregnancy Ghana.

In imposing a blanket prohibition on the freedom of expression and personal liberty of persons outside an alleged gender binary, the Bill fails to protect or safeguard minors from harmful sexual behaviors. Rather, it limits the access of minors to age-appropriate resources and education, a guaranteed constitutional right, which would be of immense benefit to them in making informed and responsible sexual health decisions as they navigate society. The approach adopted by the Bill would leave many minors confused, vulnerable and without answers to all manner of possible legitimate questions they might have concerning gender, sex, sexual expression and orientation. A legally enforced ignorance in these matters cannot be in the best interest of the affected minors, their families, or society at large.

(iv) **Clause 14: Prohibition on the funding or sponsorship of prohibited activities under the Bill**

This clause also creates a second-degree felony for a person who funds or sponsors a prohibited activity. The scope of liability in this instance covers both legal and natural persons, with the principal officers of such bodies held jointly and severally liable. Such a provision is directly at odds with the fundamental right of persons to associate for the protection of interests as well as the right to freedom of expression, which rights are as constitutionally protected for legal persons as for natural persons. Again, the sponsors of this Bill do not demonstrate what legitimate public or governmental interest is served by prohibiting persons who wish to solidarize or show empathy with the plight or cause of LGBTQ+ persons from supporting them in diverse ways, including financially.

(v) **Clauses 15-16: Association**

Clauses 15 and 16 purport to curb the existence of groups, societies, associations, clubs, or organisations which support LGBTQ+ related activities. Clause 15 retroactively disbands such existing groups while Clause 16 prohibits formation and registration. These provisions needlessly encroach on the right to associate freely.

Article 21 of the Constitution guarantees all persons the rights to freedom of assembly and freedom of association, subject to respect for the rights and freedoms of others and for the public interest. In *Mensima and Others v. Attorney-General and Others* [1997-98] 1 GLR 159 - 218 , Bamford-Addo, JSC noted that the freedom of association “*is recognised provided the objects are not illegal or their promotion such as to involve crime or illegality. An association with criminal objects, e.g. to commit murders or thefts, would be illegal.*” [Emphasis added.] Proponents of this bill suggest that the mere existence of LGBTQ+ and related groups promotes the criminal offence of unnatural carnal knowledge. However, the prohibitions under this Bill extend unreasonably beyond the example provided by

Bamford-Addo, JSC in *Mensima*. Her example is key here as it elucidates the nature of associations that our law intends to restrict; put simply, a group of individuals meeting to further a murder is vastly different from a group of individuals meeting to advocate for a legal shift, provide a safe space for verbal expression, or develop programmes in their interest. The latter group meetings, to the extent that they do not feature criminal acts, fall within the ambit of a constitutional association. Perhaps the bill's proponents admit said constitutionality and thus are overreaching to criminalize any semblance of an LBGTTQQIAAP+ voice going forward – an impracticable task.

Moreover, it can hardly be concluded that all LGBTQ+ persons and related groups meet with the object of committing unnatural carnal acts, as suggested by the Bill. Consider a group which is formed and meets regularly to work towards decriminalising sex work – UNAIDS and Human Rights Watch are three prominent entities which have publicly espoused this position at various meetings. While prostitution offends Christian principles and present Ghanaian law, one may not reasonably infer that the meeting attendees congregate with an intention to prostitute.

Laws which limit fundamental human rights ought to be as narrowly tailored and subjected to strict constitutional test. The broad sweep of the Bill--in excess of our existing laws which already criminalise unnatural carnal knowledge--in the name of religious and family values is disturbing. Additionally, while culture invariably influences law, it is multifaceted and cannot dictate the law that governs all. Values vary even across families, so the notion of a unitary national framework of family values, paternalistically codified by our lawmakers, is an affront to democracy. Will we as a society continue to claw back against non-criminal but “undesirable” groupings until the freedom of association is wholly encumbered by religious and supposed Ghanaian family values?

(vi) Violation of Non-discrimination constitutional provisions

The Constitution contains a broad anti-discrimination clause in Article 17. Beginning in Chapter 5 of the Constitution, every person in Ghana, whatever his race, place of origin, political opinion, colour, religion, creed or gender is entitled to the fundamental human rights and freedoms enshrined the Constitution. And these rights, must be respected and upheld by the Executive, Legislature and Judiciary and all other organs of government and its agencies, and must be enforced by the Ghanaian courts.

The Constitution promises that all persons shall be equal before the law, and prohibits discrimination of every person, based on their gender, race, colour, ethnic origin, religion, creed or social or economic status. Indeed, the Supreme Court of Ghana has made a definite pronouncement on Article 17(2) of the Constitution in *T.T Nartey v Godwin Gati*, declaring that lawful discrimination was permissible so long as it did not contravene grounds included in Article 17(2).

Clauses 17 and 18 of the Bill break the promise of equal protection by prohibiting the adoption of a child by a person who belongs to one of the groups delineated by the Bill. It creates a society where some Ghanaians, based on their gender, or otherwise, are given different treatment, are subjected to restrictions, and are denied privileges and advantages.

5. **An assessment of the compatibility of the Bill with Ghana's international obligations to guarantee the respect, protection and fulfillment of human rights**

Ghana has obligations under international and regional human rights law to respect, protect, and fulfill human rights to all persons in its jurisdiction. Ghana is, therefore, obligated to ensure that the provisions of a Bill, which may become law, is in accordance with Ghana's obligations and the several international and regional human rights treaties, to which Ghana is a State Party.

The Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021, (The Bill), is incompatible with the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, United Nations Charter, International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, Convention on the Rights of the Child, International Convention on the Protection of the Rights of All Migrant Workers and Members of Their Families, African Charter on Human and People's Rights and general principles of International Law.

The Bill targets for discrimination and criminalization, people who are LGBTQ+, either perceived or real, those who question their sexuality and allies of "LGBTQ+ related activities". The Memorandum to the Bill and several clauses of the Bill including Clause 1, 6, 10, 11, and 16 are incompatible with the foundational principles of Equality and Non-discrimination in international human rights law provided under Articles 1 and 2 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR), which emphasise that '[a]ll human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights', and '[e]veryone is entitled to all the rights and freedoms set forth in this Declaration [UDHR], without distinction of any kind, such as race, colour, sex, language, religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, property, birth or other status'. The targeted discrimination and criminalisation of LGBTQ+ and related activities is also incompatible with the equality and nondiscrimination provisions in international and regional instruments to which Ghana is a State Party including Articles 2, 3, and 26 of the International Covenant on Civil and

Political Rights (ICCPR); Article 1 (3) of the UN Charter; Articles 2 (2) and 4 of the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESR); Article 2 of the Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC); Articles 1(1) and 7 of the International Convention on the Protection of the Rights of All Migrant Workers and Members of Their Families; and Articles 2, 3, 18 (3)-(4), 28 of the African Charter on Human and People's Rights (ACHPR). The Bill's incompatibility with equal protection and non-discrimination principles along with the criminalization of persons based on their real or perceived sexual orientation is likely to lead to increased violence and discrimination against such persons in Ghana if the Bill becomes law. In its shadow report to the United Nations Human Rights Council in 2017 prior to the review of Ghana's human rights record under the Universal Periodic Review (UPR) mechanism, Ghanaian civil society organizations reported that LGBTQ+ persons were subjected to violence and discrimination, noting:

"Despite the establishment of a reporting system to collate human rights abuses against minorities including LGBT persons, LGBT people in Ghana still face violence, human rights abuse, discrimination and heightened hate/homophobic speech from government officials and religious leaders which incites violence and homophobia against the LGBT community in Ghana" (para.2, Sexual Orientation and Gender Identity in Ghana, Factsheet – UPR 2017, Ghana)

When the violence perpetrated against LGBTQ+ persons was brought to the attention of Ghana during the review of its human rights record, Ghana accepted a recommendation to "[t]ake the steps necessary to protect lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender and intersex persons from violence and discrimination on the basis of their sexual orientation and gender identity" (para 146.59/ /HRC/37/7).

However, Ghana has not taken any proactive measures to stem the violence and discrimination against persons based on their real or perceived sexual orientation. In 2018, Human Rights Watch reported in its study "No choice but to deny who I am", the

violence and discrimination perpetrated against LGBTQ+ persons in Ghana. In one instance they narrated the ordeal of thirty-year-old Pearl, thus:

In mid-September 2009, the District Chief Executive in my town called me for a meeting...I was taken to the conference room and made to sit in the middle of about 50 people. They asked me if I was a lesbian, and I said no. One police officer kicked me with his boot on my mouth, said I shouldn't talk. I started bleeding. Then everybody started to beat me. They took me outside, dragging me and beating me at the same time. A youth boy put a car tire around my neck and poured petrol over my body, ready to burn me. The pastor said I should confess everything before I die. (Pearl, 30-year-old woman, January 2017, Kumasi, Ghana (Introduction to report, p.1, No choice but to deny who I am, Human Rights Watch, 2018)

Violence associated with discrimination based on gender identity and sexual orientation are reportedly on the rise:

"...the rising number of hate crimes based on sexual orientation and gender identity correlates with a steep rise in ultraconservative political and religious groups using their platforms to promote bigotry, dehumanize persons on the basis of sexual orientation, gender identity or expression, and foster a stigma and intolerance among constituencies. Such discourse sometimes is used as a means to bolster popularity and detract attention from pressing economic and internal political problems..." (A/HRC/38/43, para. 38, United Nations Independent Expert on Protection against Violence and Discrimination based on Sexual Orientation and Gender Identity).

Similarly, in the wake of violence against persons based on their perceived or real sexual orientation or gender identity in Africa, the African Commission on Human and Peoples' Rights (ACHPR) condemned "...the increasing incidence of violence and other human rights violations, including murder, rape, assault, arbitrary imprisonment and other forms of persecution of persons on the basis of their imputed or real sexual orientation or

gender identity” (Resolution 275, adopted at the 55th Ordinary Session of the African Commission on Human and Peoples’ Rights in Luanda, Angola, 28 April to 12 May 2014).

Despite concern about the likelihood of an increase in violence and discrimination against LGBTQ persons if the Bill becomes law, proponents of the Bill say a provision in Clause 22 of the Bill which imposes a maximum prison sentence of three years on a person who “verbally or physically, abuses, assaults or harasses, a person accused of an offence under this Act;...” will deter perpetrators from acts prohibited by Clause 22. However, given the violence that continues to be perpetrated against LGBTQ+ persons even in the absence of a law criminalising LGBTQ+ persons in Ghana, this Bill, if it becomes law, will provide anti-LGBTQ+ vigilantes a weapon to perpetrate violence and discrimination against LGBTQT persons.

The Bill also seeks to criminalize fundamental freedoms including any form of association with LGBTTQQIAAP+ persons as well as funding or engaging in any form of advocacy for the respect, protection, and fulfilment of the rights of LGBTQ+ persons. The criminalisation of freedom of association is incompatible with the freedom of association and assembly provisions in Article 20 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR); Article 22 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights; and Article 10(1) of the African Charter on Human and People’s Rights (ACHPR). It is also incompatible with Article 15 (1) of the Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC) which enjoins State Parties, of which Ghana is one, to “...recognize the rights of the child to freedom of association and to freedom of peaceful assembly.”

As well, the criminalization of advocacy for the rights of LGBTQ+ persons and allies is incompatible with the freedom of opinion and expression provisions in Article 19 of UDHR; Article 19 of ICCPR; Article 5 of ICERD; Article 7 of CEDAW; Article 13 of CRC; and Article 9 of ACHPR.

Clause 6(1)(a)(i) of the Bill which criminalises same-sex relations between consenting adults is also incompatible with Article 12 of UDHR; Article 17 of ICCPR; and Article 16 of CRC.

The interpretation of 'Ghanaian family values' in Clause 2; Clause 3(1) (2) (3) and elsewhere is vague and overbroad and is incompatible with a general principle in international law that requires legal certainty.

Ghana has obligations under international and regional human rights law to respect, protect, and fulfill human rights to all persons without discrimination. The duty to respect is a negative obligation which prohibits Ghana or any of its organs including in this case, the Parliament, from enacting legislation that would violate rights of persons in its jurisdiction. Although the Bill is a Private Member's Bill and was not initiated by or presented to Parliament by the Executive, it would still be construed as state-sponsored discrimination if Parliament passes the Bill and the president assents to it. In addition to the several incompatible provisions of the Bill with international and regional human rights treaties to which Ghana is a State Party, the Bill will likely weaponise violence and discrimination against LGBTQ+ persons as well as heterosexuals and make it nearly impossible for the state to respect, protect, and fulfill its human rights obligations to all persons in its jurisdiction.

6. Socio-economic and health implications to minority groups

Though data produced in consort with Ghanaian state institutions are scarce, people with diverse SOGIE are likely subjected to higher forms of discrimination in the workplace and education. Abundant reports of this have been documented by civil society organizations (See Solace Initiative 2019; Solace Brothers Foundation 2015; Solace Initiative 2019; Isaack 2018; Nwosu-Juba and Anglophone West African LBQT Research Collective 2019), and the absence of state-authored data is a symptom of an unwillingness to devote time and resources to testing and verifying/disproving the overwhelming consensus from local and international NGOs on the subject in Ghana. This is evident by

the almost celebratory tone of local articles that report on the expulsion of students (GhanaWeb 2013) and the firing of persons based on perceived or imputed SOGIE (HotFM.com 2021). The passage of this Bill will doubtlessly exacerbate this trend ushering in discrimination in the domain of education, employment, health, and housing, compromising the rights of the groups targeted, which are guaranteed by the International Covenant on Economic Social and Cultural Rights, the Convention on the Rights of the Child and Chapter 5 of Ghana's Constitution. Furthermore, the bill could also facilitate blackmail due to Clause 5, which imposes the duty to report persons suspected of having banned identities or engaging in banned activities.

7. Conclusion

1. The Bill is in direct conflict with a number of constitutionally-protected fundamental freedoms and human rights.
2. The provisions of the Bill are also incompatible with a number of international human rights instruments to which Ghana is a State Party.
3. The Bill is certain to negatively impact Ghana's reputation at the international level and have a direct impact on its relationship with many foreign nations as well as its ability to attract foreign aid, foreign investors and tourists.
4. The Bill could be considered as support for state-sponsored discrimination.
5. The Bill, if passed, would make a mockery of the supreme law of the land and go beyond making the lives of LGBTQ+ persons extremely uncomfortable. Their liberty would be at stake merely due to their existence and would significantly impact their ability to freely engage in day-to-day life.
6. LGBTQ+ persons would no longer benefit from the community support and assistance received from allies and funders, assistance which has provided a physical, emotional and psychological lifeline.

It is the considered position of the Human Rights Coalition that the Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021 is irredeemably flawed, unconstitutional and needless. It does not address any pertinent cultural, socio-economic or political challenge the country faces, as Private Member Bills were envisioned to address. We respectfully ask the Committee to not recommend its passage.

Human Rights Coalition

1. [REDACTED]
2. [REDACTED]
3. Amnesty International, Ghana
4. [REDACTED] a
5. [REDACTED]
6. [REDACTED]
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